

**COMPREHENSIVE TREATMENT GENERALIZED PERIODONTITIS
AND CLINICAL AND RADIOLOGICAL EVALUATION OF
EFFECTIVENESS**

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Annotation: Objective of the study Comparison of the effectiveness of conservative and surgical treatment of generalized periodontitis of subjects and methods of II-III degrees.

Materials and method: Clinical X-ray examination of 18-64-year-old patients with generalized periodontitis was carried out in 123 persons. All patients were divided into 2 groups by age, with Group 1 being 18-39 years of age with generalized periodontitis of II-III degree (n=58) and group 2 being 40-64 years of age with generalized periodontitis of II-III degree (n=65). The analysis of clinical and X-ray parameters was carried out by comparison with the clinical features of the course of pathological processes in age groups and subgroups, that is, age and periodontitis. Comprehensive treatment of patients was planned, depending on the nature of the course of the disease, professional oral hygiene, local antibacterial therapy (0.05% chlorhexidine, etc.), anti-inflammatory therapy of periodontal pockets. According to the indications, antibacterial therapy, anti-inflammatory therapy by nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, bruxism, sprints of movable teeth, etc. were carried out. As surgical treatment, vestibular plastic surgery, fresnulotomy and flap surgery were performed. Defects in the dentition were removed artificially.

Results and considerations: During the study period, the chief complaints of patients in the clinical group of 18-39 years old were gingival pain, bleeding (sometimes spontaneous bleeding), swelling of the alveolar protrusion mucosa, pronounced migration, independent of sanitary measures and food intake. The

medical history revealed that he had been treated by a general dentist before undergoing specialized periodontal treatment. At the same time, the means of treatment were limited to the removal of dentin deposits, sometimes closed curettage. As for the mobility of the teeth, some patients wore sprints. No patients were under the control of the clinic until they contacted a periodontologist. Laboratory tests revealed poor oral hygiene in all patients with Grade II and III systemic periodontitis in this age group. The green cinnabar index was 3.9 ± 0.4 , and abundant dental deposits were observed in patients with grade 3-4 tooth mobility and open trichomes. At the time of examination, tooth mobility was high. The depth of the periodontal pocket was 6-10 mm. Bone defects in laboratory tests usually reached the edge of the molars. Vertical bone defects in these sites were 4-7 mm. In laboratory tests of oral organs, most patients with systemic periodontitis noted the presence of non-antiseptic caries fossa, a defect in the previously applied seal. In some cases, there is a decrease in the depth of the oral vestibule (especially in the front teeth of the lower jaw), a significant decrease in the width of the mucosal chain in the front teeth of the upper and lower jaws, keratosis of the mucous membrane of the alveolar process. Clinical observations of patients with generalized periodontitis aged 40-64 show that the chief complaints of patients in this group are associated with exposure to the root of the tooth, bleeding from the gums, bad breath, tooth migration and loss, and the presence of tooth defects. The duration of morbidity in this group at the time of seeking specialist help ranged from 8 to 20 years. From an objective survey of the oral organs, it was shown that in the group of older people, in comparison with young people, symptomatic gingivitis with pronounced signs of inflammation, atrophic gingivitis with a significant retreat of soft tissues is observed. In the elderly, there are many dental deposits in the anterior part of the mandible, the depth of the periodontal pocket is shallow, the bone loss rate is high, and the agitation of the tooth is remarkable. H). The figure shows a rather typical clinical situation in which aging or pathological conditions (due to

inflammatory processes in periodontal disease), bone atrophy of the alveolar process, traumatic occlusion are combined. In this case, as a result of the latter, pathological alveolar bone pockets are formed in the area of 21,23 teeth. A distinctive feature of this group of patients is the absence of evidence of proper orthodontic treatment. From the medical history of the patients who visited, it can be seen that in 96% of patients, orthodontic treatment was not taken into account at all at the pre-treatment stage and was an integral and sometimes major part of the planned treatment measures. Thus, the high percentage of patients who do not have full-fledged orthodontic treatment is useful when patients who are performing dental treatment of high incisors of the lower jaw consult a parodontologist about the mobility of the lower jaw incisors. The attempts of the parodontologist in this situation are surprising, and the cause of the loss of the front group of the upper jaw can also be considered not an inflammatory process of periodontitis, but a traumatic obstruction. The hygiene index is high in the tested 2 groups, which indicates that the level of oral hygiene in different age groups is insufficient. When the value of the Green vermilion index was analyzed in young people, the plaque index was significantly higher than the tartar index, but the reverse relationship was observed in the elderly. The Pma index was higher in the elderly group. At the same time, the bleeding index was also high in the patient group under 39 years of age with respect to hyperemia and edema of the alveolar process mucosa. In the elderly, the gums are pale pink, and soft tissue atrophy and significant regression are often observed. This is clearly due to the absence of deep vegetation disorders. The average depth of the periodontal pocket is also shallower in the elderly. The Russell periodontal index was significantly higher in the elderly group. Thus, analyzing the results of laboratory tests and X-ray examinations of patients with generalized periodontitis in the 40-64 years of age 1st and 2nd degree, it can be concluded that generalized periodontitis is characterized by a long-term chronic course, in which the dystrophic process prevails over inflammatory periodontitis. Comparing the

indicators of the initial state of periodontal tissue in different age groups, it was found that the oral hygiene condition worsened in patients with higher age groups, but at the same time the intensity of the inflammatory response decreased. This was also confirmed by the results of X-ray examination. In patients of the younger age group, pronounced destruction of the alveolar bone, active foci of osteoporosis, absorption of the alveolar cavity in the range of 1/2 to 1/2 of the length of the root, vertical bone resorption, multiple bone pockets 3). In the X-ray examination of patients with generalized periodontitis in the elderly, in addition to the aforementioned symptoms, sclerotic bone reconstruction is observed, and the mixed type of bone resorption is a combination of horizontal and vertical bone resorption of the alveolar process. After complex treatment, changes in the indicators that characterize the state of periodontal tissues were observed in all patient groups 6 and 12 months after the end of treatment. With or without surgery, the results of treatment were evaluated separately. After the end of conservative treatment, the depth of the periodontal pocket of the patient, the degree of tooth shaking, and the presence or absence of dentin deposition were measured. Diagnostic indicators were used to examine periodontal conditions: periodontal indicators (Russel, 1956), Schiller-Pisarev test, PMA indicators (S. A., et al. Parma, 1960), an indicator of bleeding and suppuration of the gums. Oral hygiene status is determined by Yu.A. Fedorov and V.V. Volodkina (1970) S. et al. Green, J. It was evaluated according to the method of Vermillion (1964) (table). In the conservative treatment, the mobility of the tooth after the treatment was not investigated because the sprint was attached to the movable tooth. Immediately after the end of conservative treatment in patients with degree generalized periodontitis, an improvement in the parameters of the Schiller-Pisarev test was observed (1.97 ± 0.15 in patients with GP degree II and 2.11 ± 0.17 in patients with GP degree iii). There was an improvement in oral hygiene level (S. Green, J. "I do not know. The PMA index and other periodontal indicators tended to decline. At the same time,

according to the results of the X-ray examination, the depth of the bone pocket has not changed. Indicators of bleeding and suppuration are changing in the direction of improvement. In general, the periodontal condition of GP patients of grade ii to iii immediately after the end of conservative treatment was characterized mainly by remission of the underlying disease accompanied by deterioration of oral hygiene. Periodontal tissue condition 6 months after the end of conservative treatment was characterized by elevated Schiller-Pisarev test and gingival bleeding. Clinically, in the long term after the end of conservative treatment, all indicators deteriorated. When analyzing the radiological parameters of the long-term periodontal condition after the end of conservative treatment, further significant loss of bone tissue in the region of the pathological alveolar bone pocket was observed. In some cases, the formation of defects was observed in the bone tissue of the alveolar bone process. In the lower jaw, the following conditions of radiation are observed: in the lower jaw, unlike the upper jaw, bone atrophy of the alveolar process is mixed. In particular, bone atrophy at a horizontal level of Sh-1 degree is observed in the frontal region. Movable Sh-1U class 12.11, 21 teeth were repaired with a bonding system before the start of treatment, and the most movable 12 teeth were extracted. The sprint was supplemented with adhesive bridges instead of the lost 22 teeth. On the outside of the lower jaw, various situations were observed. Bone atrophy was characterized by the formation of vertical pockets of considerable depth (more than 4 mm). At the same time, the focus of bone destruction is clearly caused by chronic pericardial inflammatory processes in the region of 48 teeth, in the region of 48 teeth preserved, and in the region of the distal root of 47 teeth. The clinical situation in this case is exacerbated by the further formation of bone pockets in the area of the 47th tooth that extend beyond the tip of the designated root. In the region of the 46th tooth, bone pockets perpendicular to the distal region of the root are confirmed, in addition to this, bone resorption perpendicular to the fur region of the 46th tooth is observed. Clinically, these teeth

do not have mobility. A similar situation is observed in the left lower jaw. At the same time, the X-ray image practically reflects the condition of the lower jaw on the right, except for the budding and dystopia of the 48th tooth.

Conclusion: 1. Rehabilitation of patients with generalized temporomandibular arthritis requires the participation of temporomandibular joint specialists, orthopaedic dentists and orthopaedic dentists at all stages of treatment. 2. Mandatory participation of hygienists and gynecologists, taking into account the depth and intensity of the pathology, it is necessary to conduct clinic observations at least 6 times in 1 month. 3. Conservative treatment or cleavage of the tooth does not bring about the actual stabilization of the disease state in the generalized periodontitis of n degrees, and in some cases promotes the progress of asymptomatic bone tissue destruction. 4. Surgical interventions, such as careful removal of morbidly altered tissue from the bone pocket, followed by replacement with bone conduction material and in combination with other therapeutic agents, help to reduce the intensity of bone tissue destruction and in some cases create conditions for periodontal tissue regeneration..

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